

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING A SECOND LANGUAGE TO CHILDREN IN A LARGE GROUP OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: Much attention is paid to the early learning of foreign languages, especially English, by preschool children. It is believed that through language learning, a child not only learns new words and phrases, but also develops his ability to hear, understand, think and communicate.

Keywords: students, foreign language, language, child, communication, expression, hearing, understanding, thinking, preschool education, didactic games, verbal, motor skills, educator.

When teaching English to children in the senior and preparatory groups of preschool educational organizations, it is necessary to create an effective language learning environment using modern and interesting methods. Children's oral speech, vocabulary, listening and comprehension skills are developed step by step.

When teaching a second language to children in preschool educational organizations, it is advisable to pay attention to the following tasks:

- Increasing children's English vocabulary;
- Introducing and consolidating key words and phrases for each topic;
- Making language learning interesting through didactic games and practical exercises;
- Developing children's fine motor skills, attention and aesthetic taste through developmental tasks;
- Combining independent activities with the participation of a teacher or parent.

Taking into account the age characteristics of preschool children, their interest in learning, short attention span and need for play, the following principles are followed in the methodological approach:

- Teaching through play is the most effective and natural form of learning for children;
- Demonstration - understandable presentation of the topic through pictures, symbols, movements and QR codes;
- Cooperation - active participation of the educator or parent in children's activities;
- Differential approach - each child learns at a pace appropriate to his or her abilities;
- Integration - language learning is combined with other developmental activities (art, nature, mathematics, physical development).

The use of games in the process of teaching a second language to children in preschool educational organizations is highly effective. These include:

ABC hopscotch

Purpose:

- To develop children's ability to remember, recognize and pronounce English letters;
- To reinforce learning through movement.

Required equipment:

- Alphabet letters (A–Z) written on the floor or ground.
- Any game tokens (pebbles, small soft balls).

Procedure:

1. The teacher writes/sticks the letters of the alphabet on the floor or ground in a hopscotch pattern (a simple jumping game).
2. Each child, when it is their turn, throws a small pebble at a letter.
3. The child jumps to that letter, says the letter and comes up with a word (if taught). For example: “B – Ball!”
4. After that, they jump back again.
5. The next child takes the turn.
6. At each stage, a new letter is selected, and thus all letters are learned or reinforced.

Sensory bag

Objective:

- Children will recognize and practice writing the letters A, B, C... in English.
- Sensory senses and fine motor skills will develop.
- Learn to pronounce the sounds of letters in English correctly.

Required equipment:

- Ziplock bag (sealable plastic bag)
- Colored paint or shampoo
- Prepared letter templates (optional)
- Scotch tape for sticking to a table or smooth surface

Procedure:

1. The educator or parent pours colored paint or shampoo into a ziplock bag and seals it tightly;
2. The bag is placed on a flat surface (table or wall);
3. The educator says the letters A, B, C... in turn;

4. The child writes the letter on the bag with his finger or a stick;
5. The educator says to the child "Find letter B!" (Find the letter B!)
6. The child swipes the paint with his finger, looking for the hidden letter, and says: "B! B is for Ball!"

In conclusion, as a requirement of today, if we develop the skills of teaching children a second language from preschool education, it will give positive results for children. It will be easier for them to learn a second language in the future. A language teacher who teaches children a language is required, first of all, to know the methodology of teaching children. As we noted above, teaching children a language requires a different approach. It is required that the pronunciations coming out of children's speech are completely in English. All of the above points serve to raise children as a well-rounded generation in the future.

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